

Sb-based Interband Cascade Lasers to Cover the 3-5 μm Spectral Window

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Semiconductor laser sources for the critical 3-5 μm spectral range are evolving and improving rapidly, with significant advancements reported within the last year for three fundamentally different approaches: the intersubband quantum cascade laser (QCL),¹ the type-I quantum well (QW) diode laser,² and the interband cascade laser (ICL).³ Of these three, the most promising candidate to cover the entire wavelength range is the antimonide-based type-II ICL as designed and grown at the Naval Research Laboratory (NRL). Broad area devices have already demonstrated threshold power densities (P_{th} = current density \times voltage) which will enable room temperature (RT) continuous-wave (CW) operation from 2.9 out to 4.6 μm (Fig. 1). The ICL architecture appears uniquely poised not only to offer complete spectral coverage (3 – 5 μm) but also to operate with low power dissipation. Some of the most recent ICLs display $P_{\text{th}} < 0.4 \text{ kW/cm}^2$ at 300 K ($\lambda \sim 3.6 - 4.0 \mu\text{m}$), which is more than 20 times lower than the best P_{th} reported to date for QCLs operating at the same temperature. For this reason, the ICL approach is favored for applications demanding low power and excess heat dissipation, *e.g.*, for long battery lifetimes in the field.

The RT threshold current densities (j_{th}) of the most recent NRL 5-stage broad area ICLs have been pushed below 200 A/cm², with a record best of 146 A/cm² for a device emitting at $\lambda =$

Fig.1 Pulsed threshold power vs. wavelength for broad-area 5-stage ICLs at 300 K. Data are shown for several generations of NRL ICLs. The dashed line represents the estimated maximum P_{th} for RT CW operation for narrow ridges.

Fig.2 Maximum CW operating temperatures as a function of year for NRL Type-II mid-IR lasers. Shown also are reported data from Maxion, JPL and Würzburg.

¹ N. Bandyopadhyay, Y. Bai, B. Gokden, A. Myzaferi, S. Tsao, S. Slivken, and M. Razeghi, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **97**, 131117 (2010).

² T. Hosoda, G. Kipshidze, L. Shterengas, and G. Belenky, *Electron. Lett.* **46**, 1455 (2010).

³ M. Kim, C.L. Canedy, C.S. Kim, W.W. Bewley, J.R. Lindle, J. Abell, I. Vurgaftman, J.R. Meyer, *Phys. Procedia* **3**, 1195 (2010).

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3.99 μm . Epitaxial-side-up narrow ridges fashioned from this material, with gold electroplating for heat dissipation, operated in CW mode to 107 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. This extends the NRL progression towards high cw operating temperatures by 35 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, and is significantly higher than for any other interband mid-IR semiconductor laser reported to date (Fig. 2). Such dramatic improvements have been driven by the introduction of various design modifications and optimizations [patents pending] that have reduced j_{th} and P_{th} to values much lower than any achieved elsewhere. A short-cavity ($L_{\text{cav}} = 0.5 \text{ mm}$) narrow ridge with one HR-coated facet reached threshold at 25 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ at a cw input power of only 29.6 mW, which compares to the lowest reported value for a type-I diode emitting beyond 3 μm of about 80 mW⁴ and the best QCL result of 830 mW.⁵ The substantial advantage over QCLs is attributable to the ICL's lower current density threshold ($< 200 \text{ A/cm}^2$ vs. $> 700 \text{ A/cm}^2$), and especially its lower voltage threshold ($\approx 2.1 \text{ V}$ vs. $\approx 10 \text{ V}$).

Narrow ridges were fabricated using a combination of dry etching by Cl-based inductively coupled plasma and a phosphoric-acid-based clean-up etch. The ridges were then electroplated with a 5- μm -thick layer of gold. Recent work has employed two methods for obtaining narrow spectral lines corresponding to single-mode operation. First, distributed-feedback lasers were fabricated by etching 4th-order gratings into both sidewalls of the narrow ridges. For CW operation at $T = -23 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, up to 32 mW of single-mode output was obtained in a spectral region overlapping the strong methane absorption lines near $\lambda \approx 3.315 \mu\text{m}$, as illustrated in Figs. 3 and 4. Second, we also obtain single-mode output by coupling a Fabry-Perot ICL to a rectangular ring resonator. The device operating simultaneously in the Fabry-Perot and ring cavities emits in a single mode because the ring resonator free spectral range is comparable to the width of the gain spectrum. A number of different ring cavities with various ridge widths, ring widths, and rectangular ring dimensions have displayed single-mode output, with cw powers up to 5 mW.

Fig. 3 CW spectral density as a function of wavelength at $T = -23 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for a narrow-ridge laser with 4th-order gratings etched on both sidewalls and uncoated facets. Spectra are shown for 4 different excitation currents.

Fig. 4 Voltage and CW power as a function of current for the narrow-ridge DFB laser from Fig. 3.

⁴ S. Forouhar, C. Frez, K. J. Franz, A. Ksendzov, Y. Qiu, K. A. Soibel, J. Chen, T. Hosoda, G. Kipshidze, L. Shterengas, and G. Belenky, *Proc. SPIE* **7945**, 79450M (2011).

⁵ Y. Bai, S. R. Darvish, N. Bandyopadhyay, S. Slivken, and M. Razeghi, *J. Appl. Phys.* **109**, 053103 (2011).